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Annotation: *This article deals with the Russian literature of the XIX century, the great figures of the period.*

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Russian literature XIX nineteenth century - the flourishing of Russian literature, which is developing in a lively rhythm; trends, tendencies, schools, and fashions are changing at a dizzying rate; each decade has its own poetics, its own ideology, its own style of art ... Twenties and sentimentalism give way to the romanticism of the twenties and thirties; in the 1940s, Russian idealistic “wisdom” and Slavic doctrine were born; fifties - the emergence of the first novels of Turgenev, Goncharov, Tolstoy; the nihilism of the sixties was replaced by populism in the seventies, the eighties filled with the glory of the artist and preacher Tolstoy; in the nineties a new flourishing of poetry begins: the period of Russian symbolism.

At the beginning of the 19th century Russian literature experienced the positive influence of classicism and sentimentalism and was enriched with new themes and genres. artistic images and creative techniques. A new century has entered into you a wave of pre-romantic movement aimed at creating a national, unique literature in form and content and meeting its needs. artistic development is our people and society. At the same time, literary ideas of various philosophical, political and historical concepts formed in Europe in the late 19th century began to enter Russia.

Romanticism in Russia In the early 19th century , as an ideological and artistic direction in literature, the advanced part of the Russians developed a deep dissatisfaction with Russian reality. The Rise of Romanticism

AND is related to Zhukovsky's poetry. His ballads are enriched with ideas of friendship and love for the Motherland.

Realism was founded in the 30s and 40s along with Romanticism, but by the middle of the 19th century it had become a dominant trend in culture. According to him, the ideological focus is *critical realism*. At the same time, the work of great realists is full of ideas of humanism and social justice.

Nations that have been in the habit of talking about it for a while , demanding a nation, complaining about the absence of a nation in literary works - but no one thought to figure out what that word meant. "The nation of writers is a value valued by some compatriots - for others it may seem absent or even flawed" - AS Pushkin

Living literature should be the fruit of a nation, even if it is nourished but not suppressed by communication. Literature is and is literary life , but its development is limited by the one-sidedness of the imitative direction that kills the nation, without which it cannot be complete. literary life .

In the mid-1930s, critical realism found its place in Russian classical literature, opening up great opportunities for writers to express Russian life and the Russian language. national character .

The particularly effective power of the Russians is critical realism The point is that it has mastered, preserved, and continued its best traditions, putting aside progressive romanticism as the main trend:

Dissatisfaction with the present, dreaming of the future. Russian critical realism is characterized by its bright national identity. The life truth, which was the basis for the works of Russian progressive writers, generally did not conform to traditional genre-specific forms. Russian literature is therefore characterized by a frequent distortion of genre-specific forms.

VGBelinsky, who saw the transition to realism in Pushkin's poetry, strongly condemned the errors of conservative and reactionary criticism that saw Boris Godunov and Eugene Onegin as the pinnacle, and rejected the nation's primitive identification with ordinary people. Belinsky underestimated Pushkin's prose, his tales, and in general, it is true that the scale of the writer's work was in the spotlight. literary achievements and innovative beginnings that marked the further development of nineteenth-century Russian literature.

In Pushkin's poem "Ruslan and Lyudmila" there is a desire for nationalism, which is reflected in Pushkin's poetry and in the poems "Bakhchisaray Fountain". Captive of the Caucasus "Pushkin takes the position of romanticism.

Pushkin's work completes the development of Russian literature in the early nineteenth century . At the same time, Pushkin is at the forefront of Russian literature, he is the founder of Russian realism, the creator of the Russian language. literary language .

Intellectual creativity had a great influence on Tolstoy in world literature .

Dostoevsky, in his novels Crime and Punishment and The Fool, realistically portrayed a clash of bright, distinctive Russian characters.

MESaltikov-Shchedrin's work is directed against the autocratic-serfdom system.

One of the writers of the 30s is NVGogol. "Nights on a Farm Near Dikanka" is a disgusting bureaucratic world to him, and he, like AS Pushkin, entered the world of fairy tales as a romantic artist.

The activity of M.Yu. Lermontov also belongs to this period. The pathos of his poetry is moral issues about human destiny and rights. The origin of Lermontov's work is connected with the culture of European and Russian Romanticism. In the early years of V he wrote three dramas marked with the mark of romance.

The novel "Heroes of Our Time" is one of the main works of the literature of psychological realism of the XIX century .

Phase 1 belongs to the same period. critical action VG Belinsky. He had a great influence on the development of literature, social thought and the taste of reading in Russia. He was a fighter for realism, demanding simplicity and truth from literature. For him, the highest authority was Pushkin and Gogol, to whom he devoted several articles.

Examining VGBelinsky's letter to NVGogol, we see that it was directed not only against Gogol's social, political, and immoral sermons, but in many ways against his literary judgments and assessments.

In the context of post-reform life, Russian social thinking, which dominated literature and criticism, increasingly turned from the present to the past and the future to identify laws and trends. historical development .

The Russian realism of the 1860s and 1870s took significant differences from the realism of Western Europe. In the works of many realist writers of that period, there are motives that foreshadow and prepare for the transition to revolutionary romanticism and socialist realism that took place in the early 20th century . The flourishing of Russian realism in the second half of the 19th century was manifested in the brightness and scale of the novel and the story. It was at this time that the novels and stories of the greatest Russian artists of that period had a great resonance in Russia and abroad. Turgenev, Leo Tolstoy, Dostoevsky's novels and many of his stories received an immediate response after being published in Germany, France, and the United States. In the Russian novel of those years, foreign writers and critics felt the connection between the specific events of Russian reality and the developmental processes of the whole of humanity.

The flourishing of the Russian novel, the desire to penetrate the depths of the human heart, and at the same time the understanding of the social nature of society and the laws that develop accordingly, became the main distinguishing feature of Russian realism. 1860-1870.

The heroes of Dostoevsky, L. Tolstoy, Saltikov-Shchedrin, Chekhov, Nekrasov reflected on the meaning of life, conscience and justice. In the structure of the new real novel and story, their hypotheses were confirmed or rejected, and when they collided with reality, their perceptions and ideas about the world spread like smoke. Their novels should be considered the true courage of the artist. For the development of Russian realism, IS Turgenev did a lot of work with his novels. Bought the most famous novel, Fathers and Sons. It depicts a new phase of Russian life, the liberation movement . Turgenev's latest novel , Nov, was received by Russian critics. In those years, populism was the most important phenomenon of social life.

The flourishing of critical realism was also reflected in Russian poetry in the 1860s and 1970s. Saltikov-Shchedrin's work became one of the peaks of Russian critical realism in the 1960s and 1980s. The clever satirical writer skillfully asked the most pressing questions and led modern life with the help of allegories, personifications ... The pathos of accusation is inherent in the work of this writer. Among the suffocators of democracy was a sworn enemy.

In the literature of the 80s, such works as "Little things in life", "Poshekhonskaya satire" played an important role. He skillfully portrayed in them the terrible consequences of serfdom and the horrific images of the moral collapse of post-reform Russia. "The story of how a man fed 2 generals" or " Wild Landowner “Dedicated to the most important issues of Russian life, they came out to the press with great censorship difficulties.

The greatest realist writers not only reflected life in their works, but sought ways to change it.

Post-reform Russian literature, which duly continued the tradition of critical realism, was the most philosophical and social literature in Europe.

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